

THE INFLUENCE OF NONWOVEN INTERLEAF ARCHITECTURES ON THE IMPACT PERFORMANCE OF COMPOSITES

R. Archer, P. Potluri, and W.W. Sampson

School of Materials, The University of Manchester, Manchester, UK
rhys.archer@manchester.ac.uk; prasad.potluri@manchester.ac.uk; w.sampson@manchester.ac.uk

Keywords: Interleaves, Impact Damage, Carbon Fibre, Polymer Matrix Composites, Layered Structures

ABSTRACT

Structural properties of non-woven interleaves, such as their areal density and the linear density of the constituent fibres, have been identified as parameters that influence the interlaminar fracture toughness (IFT) of carbon fibre composites. We present an investigation of the influence of these properties on the damage resistance and damage toughness of composites, evaluated through impact and compression tests. The results show that when a non-woven interleaf is included within the composite, the damage resistance and tolerance of the composite is increased; the increase is greater for veils with higher areal density. These behaviours are consistent with those for IFT reported in the literature. Further, the composite interleaved with a veil absorbs more of the initial force of the impact, and results in a smaller measured impact area and has a higher residual compressive strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composites are increasingly important across sectors such as the automotive and aerospace industries [1]. These composites provide an attractive materials system, as the multi-layered structure of fabrics bonded by a polymer matrix brings opportunities to control the properties for specific applications. As demand for a material increases, so does the need to understand how it performs under stress, and specifically, how the material can be toughened without a weight penalty. One method of improving the fracture toughness of composites is to introduce a nonwoven veil between layers; this is termed ‘an interleaf layer’ within the laminate structure. It is only within the last 30 years that the potential advantages of interleaving on the interlaminar fracture toughness (IFT) [2] and damage tolerance [3] of carbon fibre composites has been investigated.

Polyester veil interleaves have been shown to improve the fundamental mechanical properties of composites. Kuwata et al. [4] found that polyester veil interleaves significantly improved mode I and mode II interlaminar toughness and proposed that the primary damage mechanism was fibre bridging. Subsequently, a preliminary study of the influence of the areal density of the veil on the properties of interleaved composites was presented by Tsotis [5], who melt-bonded polyamide and polyester veils to plies of carbon fibre and incorporated these in composites which showed improved compression after impact and decreased the impact damage area. Tsotsis noted that although increasing the areal density of the polyamide interleaves improved the compression performance of the composite, for the polyester veils the effect was negative and this was attributed to poor compatibility of the PE with the matrix. For the polyamide interleaves, the observed effects were attributed to relationship between the shear (MII) and tensile (MI) fracture toughness and impact damage mechanisms. A systematic study was presented by Ramirez et al. [6] who tested composites with interleaves of PPS veils with a range of areal densities and different fibre diameters. They found that the interlaminar fracture toughness of the composite was dependent on the areal density of the veil. From consideration of theory describing the structure of random fibre networks [7], fracture toughness was shown to exhibit a strong relationship with the fibre content at the crack tip.

Given the established dependence of measures of impact damage tolerance on the mode I and mode II fracture toughness, and noting the effect of veils on the interlaminar fracture toughness of composites reported by Ramirez et al., we expect that damage resistance and tolerance in interleaved composites should depend on the areal density of the interleaved veils. Accordingly, we present here a family of experiments to characterise the damage tolerance of composites interleaved with veils of variable areal and linear densities.

2 METHOD

2.1 Materials

Carbon fibre composites were manufactured using Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion (VARI) method. For the infusion process, a ratio of 0.66 Araldite Epoxy Resin LY564 to 0.34 Aradur 2954 hardener was used. The carbon fibre materials used were supplied by Sigmalex UK. Both a unidirectional (UD) and +/-45 orientation carbon fabric was used. The fabric layers were interleaved with non-woven PPS veils with areal density between 7 gm^{-2} and 40 gm^{-2} manufactured by Technical Fibre Products Ltd., UK. The properties of the fibre and the veils are given in Table 1 and veils are shown in Fig. 1; note that these are the same family of veils used by Ramirez et al. [5], who showed that the porosity of the veils 84 % for all samples. Table 1 includes also values for the mean 'coverage' of the veils, \bar{c} . This dimensionless quantity is the expected number of fibres covering points in the plane of the veil [5, 7] and is given by

$$\bar{c} = \frac{\bar{\beta} \omega}{\delta}, \quad (1)$$

where $\bar{\beta}$ is the areal density, ω is the diameter of the constituent veil fibres, and δ is the linear density of the fibres.

Figure 1. PPS Veils from 7 gm^{-2} (left) to 40 gm^{-2} (right)

Fibres		Veil		
Linear Density, δ ($\times 10^{-7} \text{kg}^{-1}$)	Diameter, ω (μm)	Areal Density, $\bar{\beta}$ (gm^{-2})	Coverage, \bar{c}	Thickness (μm)
1	10	7	0.7	45
		10	1.0	54
		15	1.5	84
		40	4.0	173

Table 1. PPS Fibre/Veil Characteristics

2.2 Design of samples

Square composite panels of side 400 mm were manufactured. Each was cut to give 24 specimens of dimension 55×89 mm with thickness dependent on the areal density of the interleaved veil. The samples were sufficient for 6 repeat tests at three impact energies, 5 repeats for compression tests at each impact energy and 1 specimen for microscopy, allowing investigation of damage mechanisms. The stacking sequence used was $[0, V, +45, V, 0, V, 1-45, V, 0]_2$. The thickness of these composites can be seen in comparison to the areal density of the veils interleaved in Figure 2. As shown, the thickness of the reference composite is 3 mm, and for every 10 gm^{-2} of veil that is added, the thickness of the composite is increased by $33.4 \mu\text{m}$. Due to the linearity of this relationship, composite thickness and veil areal density can be used comparatively.

Figure 2. Areal density of veils and Thickness of Composites

2.3 Testing

After manufacture, ultrasonic NDT scans were obtained using a Midas Water Jet C- Scan (Midas NDT, UK) to check for defects in the panels. Each panel was marked, and specimens cut using a diamond saw; these were labelled and tested in a drop weight impact tower (Instron CEAST 9350) with a 16 mm hemispherical impactor, following ASTM standards [8]; specimens were tested at 0 J, 8 J, 15 J, and 30 J. Indent depth was not readily recorded due to the non-uniform surface of the composite. Ultrasonic NDT scans were carried out on the specimens after impact, allowing analysis of the size and shape of the impacted area.

The residual compression strength of the composites was tested using an Instron 5982 electromechanical test frame fitted with 100 kN load cell, fixed compression platens and a compression-after-impact fixture, which secured the specimen longitudinally, following ASTM standards [9]. Nominal strain was measured from crosshead displacement; the crosshead speed was 0.5 mm/min. Testing was carried out in ambient laboratory conditions. A comparison between the impacted specimens and non-impacted specimens was carried out to evaluate the loss of strength in each specimen due to impact.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data collected from impact tests was evaluated to give the initial and maximum peak force (see Fig. 3). The introduction of interleaves of the lowest areal densities increased the initial force by approximately 1 kN; it was doubled by the introduction of the 40 gm^{-2} veil (Fig. 4). From this we can ascertain that the composite is more resistant to impact when a veil is interleaved within the structure. A similar increase in impact resistance is shown in the maximum force data (Fig.5) when the 7 gm^{-2} veil is introduced to the composite. However, only a marginal difference in force can be seen between the composites interleaved with 7 gm^{-2} and 40 gm^{-2} veils – there is no significant effect of increasing the areal density of the interleaf on the maximum force the composite experiences through impact. It is important to note that impacts at 30 J create an impact area that extends to the edges of the size of the specimen, so these values, whilst indicative, should be interpreted with caution.

Figure 3. Typical Time Force graph. Example shown is for composite with 7 gm^{-2} veil interleaved

Figure 4. Initial peak force during impact testing

Figure 5. Max force during impact testing

Figure 6 compares the maximum compressive force of the composite to the areal density of the interleaf. The linearity shown indicates that the compressive force is dependent on the areal density of the interleaf, noting the linear relationship between areal density and thickness of the composite as shown previously. Importantly, the linearity provides confidence that the effect is not due to any increase in stiffness arising from the increased thickness of the composite, since bending stiffness is proportional to the cube of the thickness. The compressive strength of the composites is increased when a veil is introduced, particularly with the introduction of the 40 gm^{-2} veil, as shown by the higher values of maximum force during compression after impact testing. This indicates that the compression damage within the composite is limited by veils of greater coverage. Note the large error bars for the non-impacted specimens due to the variability in failure position and buckling during testing. This effect is more prominent in the lower impact energies, as can be seen by comparing the gradients. It is theorised that this is due to the composite being at its ultimate breaking point after 30 J impact.

Figure 7 presents scans showing the internal damage due to impact. The composite laminates with veils interleaved throughout have a smaller impact area (Fig. 8), with the width of the impact being restricted in comparison the composite without interleaves. These scans support the data presented in showing that when a veil is introduced to the composite system, the damage experienced through impact is less than in a composite that has no interleaves.

Figure 6. Max force during Compression testing

Figure 7. Typical C-scan of 8 J impact area of composites a) without a veil, b) interleaved with 1 dtex 7 gm^{-2} veil and c) interleaved with 1 dtex 40 gm^{-2} veil

Figure 8. Impact area of composites

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

From the impact and compression data collected we have shown that introducing PPS interleaves reduces impact damage, and therefore increases the damage resistance of the composites. This has been corroborated by the c-scans that show that the internal damage size caused by impact is decreased by introducing interleaves into the composite system. This is consistent with the compression data that shows that the composites interleaved with PPS veils have greater compression strength after impact. Initial analysis indicates that this is likely dependant on the areal density of the interleaf, rather than the stiffness of the composite, however further investigation into the difference in damage mechanism when a composite system includes a veil is needed.

To further explore the effect of interleaved veils on the performance of the composites, and to further probe the relationship with the coverage of the veil, we also have in hand testing of samples made using 2 dtex, and with an altered stacking sequence.

REFERENCES

- [1] E. C. Claunch, Forecasting on Composites – Markets, Products, and Demands, *Journal of Textiles, Apparel Technology, & Manufacturing.*, **9(2)**, 2015, pp. 1-6.
- [2] O. Ishai, H. Rosenthal, N. Sela, and E. Drukker, Effect of selective adhesive interleaving on interlaminar fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy composite laminates, *Composites*, **19(1)**, 1988, pp. 49 - 54.
- [3] J.E. Masters, and R.E. Evans, A new Generation of Epoxy Composites for Primary Structural Applications: Materials and Mechanics, *Toughened Composites*, 1987, pp. 413.
- [4] M. Kuwata, and P.J. Hogg, Interlaminar toughness of interleaved CFRP using non-woven veils: Part 1. Mode-I testing, *Composites. A: Applied Science & Manufure*, **42(10)**, 2011, pp. 1551-1570.
- [5] T.K. Tsotsis, Interlayer toughening of composite materials, *Polymer Composites*, **30(1)**, 2009, pp. 71-86.
- [6] V.A Ramirez, P.J. Hogg, and W.W. Sampson, The influence of the nonwoven veil architectures on interlaminar fracture toughness of interleaved composites, *Composite Science and Technology*, **110**, 2015, pp. 103 - 110.
- [7] W.W. Sampson, *Modelling Stochastic Fibrous Materials with Mathematica*, Springer-Verlag, London, 2009.
- [8] ASTM International, Standard Test Method for Measuring the Damage Resistance of a Fiber-Reinforced Polymer Matrix Composite to a Drop - Weight Impact Event, D 7136/D7136M – 07, 2007.
- [9] ASTM International, Standard Test Method for Compressive Residual Strength Properties of Damaged Polymer Matrix Composite Plates, D 7137/D7137M – 07, 2007.